

NUTRITION OF YOUNG MOTHERS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

U.Maxamatov, A.Nematullayev, D.Raimjonov, J.Ikromov
Fergana Public Health Medical Institute. Uzbekistan. Fargona.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6629627>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022
Accepted: 02nd June 2022
Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

traffic light rule, healthy eating, vitamins, harmoniously developed generation

ABSTRACT

The nutrition of a nursing woman is also important for the healthy and harmonious development of your child. He should consume foods rich in vitamins and mineral salts during the chilla period. Because the demand for them will be high during this period. Otherwise, the metabolism in the body is disrupted. Therefore, a breastfeeding woman should consume cottage cheese, cheese, milk, eggs, vegetables, whole fruits and drink 1 glass of milk every day. Food should not be too fatty, as it has a negative effect on the absorption of lime salt in the body. Consumption of liver, honey is also beneficial. The amount of fluid to drink per day should not exceed two liters.

If you are thinking about which of the foods you eat during breastfeeding will harm your baby, remember the following traffic light rule.

Red - not at all![1.2.3]

Products in this category have a negative effect on the child;

- Wine - alcohol is administered to the child with almost 100% breast milk;
- Raw and canned onions, garlic, garlic, mayonnaise and sauces spoil the taste of milk;
- Mustard (mustard, mustard), bitter coffee, bitter chocolate, cheese, rich in various aromatic additives - spoils the taste of milk;
- Herring, seafood, salmon - salts milk;
- Raw and canned fish and shrimp - cause allergies.

Yellow - possible but with caution!

While there is no harm in this category of products, they cannot be consumed in large quantities and carelessly;

- Melon, beet, yogurt, peas, vegetable oil - an abundance of these products can cause pain and diarrhea in the abdomen;
- Pears, pomegranates, dates, rice, bread and pastries - can make a child constipated;
- Cow's milk, oranges, grapefruit, currants, eggs, salmon, fish, semolina, corn and wheat bran - can cause allergic reactions.

Green - you can eat as much as you want!

It is possible and useful to consume products in this category.[4]

- Carrots, parsley, dill - have a positive effect on the child's eyes;
- Lettuce leaves, gooseberries, currants - boosts immunity;
- Zucchini, squash, cod - have a positive effect on the development and growth of the child;

- Cottage cheese, yogurt - strengthens bones and teeth;

- Kefir, yogurt, iron, oatmeal, cauliflower - improves digestion.

Highly allergic products:[5]

- Cow's milk - causes very high allergic reactions in some children.

Try a little milk - try it and drink it with your baby;

- Egg whites - it is enough to eat one egg a week, otherwise the child may develop allergies;

- Cooked meat - if your child is prone to allergies, use frozen meat. It has lower allergen levels.

Taking care of your breasts:[6]

The care of the breasts during breastfeeding is not much different from the care of other times. Daily washing is usually sufficient. But here are a few helpful tips:

Do not rub soap on your vacuum cleaners or rub them hard, as this can dry them out and make them cracked.

If your pacifiers are delicate, it may be helpful to drip (and dry) a small amount of

milk on the pacifiers at the end of each feeding. Breastfeeding should not be painful. If you feel pain, your baby may not be adhering well (see the Adhesion section).

Use breast pads on your nipple to absorb leaking milk.

Change your chest pads frequently, especially when you feel they are wet or wet. Leaving the soles of the chest in contact with your skin can cause itching and cracking of the nipples.

Look at your breasts every day, paying attention to any redness, blemishes or any other unusual things. If they do not go away or you feel pain or become ill, consult a breastfeeding specialist or doctor.[7]

In conclusion, the following data show that proper nutrition of breastfeeding women is very important for the healthy and harmonious development of children. Therefore, one of the important tasks of each of us is to support every breastfeeding woman in this regard. Attention to them is attention to the future.

References:

1. Hygiene of children and adolescents Edited by Shaykhova G.I. T., 2011
2. Hygiene. Edited by N.M. Demidekko T., 2002
3. Баранов А.А., Намазова-Баранова Л.С., Альбицкий В.Ю., Терлецкая Р.Н. Состояние здоровья детей современной России (Серия «Социальная педиатрия», выпуск 20). М.: ПедиатрЪ. 2018; 120 с. [Baranov A.A., Namazova-Baranova L.S., Al'bitskiy V.Yu., Terlectskaya R.N. Sostoyanie zdorov'ya detey sovremennoy Rossii (Seriya «Sotsial'nayapediatriya», vypusk 20). (State of health of children in modern Russia. (Social Pediatrics series, release 20).) Moscow: Pediatr. 2018; 120 p. (In Russ.)]
4. Shoirjonovich M. U., Abdulkhamidovna K. M. Flatulence in Children and Adolescents and its Prevention //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 83-85.
5. Shoirjonovich M. U., Abdulkhamidovna K. M. Platelet deficiency disease among children and adolescents and measures to prevent it //Eurasian Medical Research Periodical. – 2021. – Т. 3. – С. 37-39.

6. Махаматов У. С., Хатамова У. В. EMERGENCY SITUATIONS RESPONSIBILITIES AND PREVENTION MEASURES //Мировая наука. – 2018. – №. 12. – С. 33-36.
7. Хатамова У. В., Махаматов У. С. FOOD POISONING AND ITS PREVENTION AND DISPOSAL METHODS //Мировая наука. – 2018. – №. 12. – С. 85-87.
8. Шерматов Р. М., Махаматов У. Ш. СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ МИКРОБИОЦЕНОЗА У НЕДОНОШЕННЫХ И НОРМАЛЬНОРОЖДЁННЫХ НОВОРОЖДЕННЫХ ДЕТЕЙ //Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. – 2016. – №. 5-2. – С. 76-79.
9. Махаматов У. С., Хатамова У. В. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF URGENT MEDICAL INSTRUCTIONS IN EMERGENCY STATIONS //Мировая наука. – 2018. – №. 12. – С. 37-40.
10. Хатамова У. В., Махаматов У. С. VITAMINS AND HUMAN HEALTH //Мировая наука. – 2018. – №. 12. – С. 83-85.